

A haptic stiffness display device for remote palpation in minimally invasive surgery

Max Jäger^[0000–0003–2203–4140] and Hartmut Witte^[0000–0001–6055–2921]

Biomechanics Group, Technische Universität Ilmenau, Max-Planck Ring 12, 98693 Ilmenau, Germany {max.jaeger, hartmut.witte}@tu-ilmenau.de

Abstract. In tumor surgery in the lower sections of the pharynx and in the brain, surgeons currently use endoscopic instruments which limit their access to haptically perceptible tissue properties. This haptic information is useful to discriminate tissue types, such as healthy and tumorous tissue, and can thus be used to assess tumor margins and tumor resection progress during surgery. The use of feedback devices to provide haptic impressions offers opportunities to restore the sense of touch in minimally invasive surgery, making it a field of high research interest. In our project, we aim to develop a haptic device for stiffness display to assist intraoperative tissue discrimination.

Keywords: Haptic feedback · Stiffness display · Tumor surgery · Remote palpation.

1 Introduction

Tissue discrimination during tumor surgery via manual palpation is a viable part of the process to completely excise tumorous tissue. In minimally invasive surgery, and especially in the robotically assisted case, the surgeon cannot touch the tissue directly and has to rely on visual cues or tool-tissue interactions transferred through endoscopic instruments to their hands. Haptic feedback can improve tissue discrimination capabilities by restoring the sense of touch and thus, enable remote, device-based palpation [1, 3, 7].

In the joint project Sensorized Surgery¹, we aim to enhance the available patient data and the ways they are displayed to surgeons in ENT and neurosurgery applications. These two surgical fields can benefit greatly from added haptic feedback because the surgeons only have limited direct access to the tissue with their fingers, and endoscopic instruments are primarily used. Our group investigates and implements haptic feedback for real-time display of tissue mechanical properties. We aim to develop a principle of operation that allows integration with existing surgical instrument handles and can easily be adopted in interfaces of surgical robots. In this paper, we outline the current state of our research and describe planned next steps.

¹ <https://sensorisierte-chirurgie.de/en/home-english>

2 Method

To obtain mechanical properties of tissue, several methods exist [6]. Since healthy and tumorous tissues display differing stiffness, we aim to acquire stiffness measurements and display them as stiffness, instead of encoding measured values into, e.g., vibration [4]. Using haptic feedback can reduce cognitive load (see, e.g., [2]), and designing a device to display haptic information as unaltered as possible should facilitate this and lead to intuitive use of the device for the task.

For our current experiments, we use stiffness measurements based on a 6 DoF force-torque sensor and a custom 4 DoF positioning system (Fig. 1, step 1).

Fig. 1. Our process from stiffness measurement to display with a haptic device. The sample used here is a soft silicone disk with a stiffer, star-shaped silicone inclusion (also described in [5]).

The principle is described in [5]. From multiple indentation depth settings δ and force measurements F , stiffness k can be derived by fitting a polynomial (e.g. quadratic) to the data for each measurement position (Eqs. (1), (2) and Fig. 1, step 2).

$$F_{fit}(\delta) = a \cdot (\delta + c)^2 + b \cdot (\delta + c) \quad (1)$$

$$k = \frac{dF_{fit}}{d\delta} = 2a \cdot (\delta + c) + b. \quad (2)$$

where a , b , c are the fit parameters. The parameter c takes into account that contact, determined using a force magnitude threshold, already results in an indentation $\delta|_{contact} > 0$. Using the quadratic polynomial fit, we achieve coefficients of determination $R^2 \geq 0.995$. A series of measurements on an object can be used to collect a point cloud of stiffness values (Fig. 1, step 3). The user then interacts with the gathered data through a haptic device, the pose of which is tracked to determine the fingertip’s position relative to the point cloud. To display the measured stiffness, we exert a force at the user’s index fingertip (Fig. 1, step 4). The force is generated by a series elastic actuator consisting of a brushless DC motor and a linear tension spring. Forces are transmitted from the motor’s pulley to the spring and from the spring to the finger interface

by strings. The force at the interface $F_{interface}$ thus depends on the interface's deflection $d_{interface}$ (measured by a Hall effect sensor) and the motor's shaft angle θ (measured by the motor's shaft encoder), see Eqs. (3), (4) and Fig. 2.

$$F_{fingertip} = \Delta l \cdot k_s \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta l = \theta r - d_{interface} \quad (4)$$

where Δl - spring deflection; k_s - spring constant; r - motor pulley radius.

Fig. 2. Schematic of the influences of the finger interface's position and motor shaft angle on the force at the fingertip interface.

3 Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange

To evaluate the haptic device regarding its intended purpose of tissue discrimination based on stiffness, we plan a user study to compare manual palpation and device assisted, virtual palpation. Subjects should (at least in part) be surgeons to ensure that the needs of the target users are taken into account. We invite psychophysicists to discuss possible improvements of our approach for tissue discrimination. Prior to this study, the device's functionality and overall usability must be optimized so that its performance during the palpation task is ideally not affected by factors such as cumbersome handling. To achieve this, we plan smaller-scale user studies focused on usability optimization. Current implementations of the stiffness display (e.g. Fig. 1, step 4) realize a standalone device that displays prerecorded data. We plan to attach the force/torque sensor to the haptic device directly to test remote palpation with real-time data. We invite medical device manufacturers to discuss the possibilities of integrating the described operating principle into handles for endoscopic instruments.

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